

Electronic Pipe Organ using Audio Feedback

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new electronic pipe organ based on positive audio feedback. Unlike typical resonance of a tube of air, we use audio feedback introduced by an amplifier, a lowpass filter, as well as a loudspeaker and a microphone in a closed pipe to generate resonant sounds without any physical air blows. Timbre of this sound can be manipulated by controlling the parameters of the filter and the amplifier. We introduce the design concept of this audio feedback-based wind instrument, and present a prototype that can be played by a MIDI keyboard.

1. INTRODUCTION

Audio feedback is a positive feedback of acoustic signal in a sound loop between an audio input and an output: signals received by the microphone are amplified, played through the loudspeaker, then received by the microphone again to be endlessly re-amplified.

Use of audio feedback is quite common in popular music – especially with electric guitars and, while much less common, found in electroacoustic music, too: examples include *Pendulum Music* (1968) by Reich, which feature phasing feedback tones between suspended microphones and speakers [1]. However, audio feedback has been rarely used as sound producing mechanism for traditional musical instruments. For example, most wind/pipe instruments usually make sound by the player’s air blow: more specifically, there exists certain type of resonator (e.g., a tube) in which air column vibrates by the air blown into a mouth-piece set.

This paper describes the design of a new electronic pipe organ using audio feedback: instead of physically blowing air into the pipes, we use positive audio feedback loop of microphone-speaker to produce resonating sound. The MIDI-compatible prototype instrument presented features four pipes of different lengths to generate sounds with different pitches, and can be played with a MIDI keyboard.

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2. RELATED WORK

The organ is a musical instrument with a long history. Based on its sound-producing mechanism, organs can be categorized into several groups such as pipe, reed, electronic, and digital organs. Virtually none of these, however, utilizes the idea of acoustic feedback we propose.

Examples of acoustic feedback used for musical instruments include the hybrid Virtual/Physical Feedback Instruments (VPFI) [2], in which a physical instrument (e.g., a pipe) and virtual components (e.g., audio DSP processors such as a lowpass filter) constitute a feedback cycle. The *Audible EcoSystemics n.2* is a live electronic music based only on Larsen tones (i.e., sound generated by audio feedback) [3].

In [4], Overholt et al. documents the role of feedback in actuated musical instruments. While the examples introduced feature feedback through electromagnetic actuators (not acoustic ones), they show the potential of more sophisticated control on audio feedback.

Audio feedback has been used to design music controllers. In [5], the authors of this paper presented a feedback-based music controller: here, the control signal is generated by audio feedback resonance and then computer-analyzed to identify closed tone holes of a pipe interface. Although the control signal is “unwanted” in many applications and causes (sometimes annoying) sonic disturbances, the interface itself shows solid performance. [6], [7], and [8] also show controllers that measure and analyze acoustic resonance or embouchure using microphones or pressure sensors for durable and dynamic musical interactions.

Some “wind controllers,” including [9] and [10], adopt the shape of a pipe but are based on non-acoustic sensors, being independent of the acoustic sound-producing mechanism of wind instruments.

3. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Overview

Figure 1 shows the individual components of the system and the overall structure. Here a microphone is installed at one end of the pipe to measure the signal inside the pipe, which is then fed to an amplifier and a lowpass filter. At the other end of the pipe lies a small loudspeaker, which plays the amplified/filtered result of the signal from the microphone to complete an audio feedback loop. The speaker-side of the pipe is sealed to make it a closed cylinder (this will be further discussed below).

Figure 1: Individual components of the system and their connections. A microphone is installed at the open end, with a loudspeaker unit at the other end. Sound from the microphone is amplified, lowpass filtered, and played by the speaker. The instrument can be played by a MIDI keyboard.

The amplifier in the feedback loop can be controlled via MIDI messages, which enables the user to play/stop the sound with any MIDI controller. The role of lowpass filter is to reduce high-frequency components of the resonating sound, thereby preventing howling that can be introduced by excessive amplification. Moreover, the filter can also serve as a loss filter (as in digital waveguide synthesis), which simulates the damping of pressure waves in a tube [11] [12]. This suggests the potential of sound design and manipulation by adjusting filter parameters.

3.2 Implementation

Figure 2 shows a simple prototype of the idea. The “instrument” consists of four PVC pipes (with the same diameter, but different lengths) to play four different notes. The inside and outside diameters of the pipes are 3.1 and 3.7 cm, respectively.

As the transducers for feedback, we used Shure SM11 lavalier microphones and FDS28 speaker units, which were connected to MOTU Traveler digital audio interface for both audio recording and playback. The amplifiers and the biquad lowpass filters were implemented in Max/MSP.

3.3 Pitch and spectral analysis

Figure 3 shows a waveform of the sound in the longest pipe. Obviously, it is heavily clipped due to over-amplification by feedback.

We decided to make the instrument play four notes – C5 (523.25 Hz), D5 (587.33 Hz), E5 (659.26 Hz), and F5 (698.46 Hz). Here, frequency of the lowest mode of oscillation is calculated as

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{v}{4L}, \quad (1)$$

where T_1 is the period of the oscillation, v is the speed of sound, and L is the length of the pipe [13]. In theory, lengths of the pipes should be set as 16.2, 14.5, 12.9, and

Figure 2: Prototype of the instrument made with pieces of PVC pipes.

Figure 3: Waveform of the sound from the longest pipe (17.5cm), which is set to play C5 note. Sound is heavily clipped and to become almost like a square wave.

12.2 centimeters, respectively, when v is 340 meters per second. However, in real experiments, the fundamental frequencies from the pipes with those lengths were different from the estimated values calculated by the equation: in fact, they showed some nonlinear characteristics and increased discretely (i.e., in a step-like fashion, by more than 30 Hz) as the length of the pipe increases.

While we think that this phenomenon may be due to some characteristics (e.g., irregular frequency response) of the transducers used, we were not able to find the reason and solve the problem. Instead, we measured the resonance frequencies of the pipes at various lengths and chose the ones with frequencies that were closest to those of desired pitches (see table 1 and figure 4 for comparison).

Magnitude spectra of the sound from two pipes are shown in figure 5. It is clear that peaks of odd-numbered harmonics are dominant, which is typical of a closed tube [13].

Length (cm)	Calculated frequency (Hz)	Measured frequency (Hz)
17.5	485.7	504
14.0	607.1	592.8
12.5	680.0	654.7
11.2	758.9	688.4

Table 1: Comparison between calculated and measured frequencies of the pipes at certain lengths.

Figure 4: In this figure, the blue dotted curve shows the calculated length of a pipe from the fundamental frequency value (by equation 1), and green stems show the measured lengths from table 1.

Figure 5: Magnitude spectra of the resonance sound from two pipes with different length and cutoff frequency, (a) 17.5 cm, 1200 Hz, and (b) 12.5 cm, 500 Hz. Gain factor is fixed at 53.97 dB.

Figure 6: Magnitude spectra when (a) gain factor is increased to 66.02 dB, and (b) cutoff frequency is decreased to 500 Hz from figure 5 (a). Gain factor changes magnitudes of high-frequency peaks, while cutoff frequency slightly alters the fundamental frequency (504 Hz to 499.3 Hz).

3.4 Control Parameters and MIDI Mapping

In this system, we use the gain factor of amplifier and the cutoff frequency of lowpass filter as the control parameters for each pipe: gain factor changes the peak magnitudes at high frequencies (i.e., above 13 kHz) thereby slightly manipulating its timbre. The cutoff frequency of lowpass filter does not change the sound much as the range is limited between 300 and 1200 Hz (to generate resonances and prevent excessive howling), but can contribute to small changes in fundamental frequency (similar to the effect of fractional delays used in digital waveguide theory) [12] (figure 6).

To make this useful as a musical instrument, the control parameters were mapped to be manipulated by MIDI messages. The first (and the simplest) mapping was to play/stop each note by turning on/off the amplifier, which can be considered as a binary mapping [14]. In addition, we tried to use velocity values to control gain factor and cutoff frequency for more “expressiveness.” Sound samples of these tones are available at:

<http://aimlab.kaist.ac.kr/~asuramk88/pipe-instrument>.

4. CONCLUSION

We presented an electronic pipe organ, which uses audio feedback loop and does not require any air blow device. The mechanism is simple in structure and easy to implement, and we believe this idea can be used for development of new wind/pipe instruments as well as experimental sound installations with pipes or tubes.

The resonance occurred by acoustic feedback in each pipe is similar to that of typical acoustic wind instruments. However, we have seen that the resulting sound is excessively clipped (mostly due to repeated amplifications through feedback), and many people commented that it did not sound “natural.” While this can be considered as a unique feature of this instrument, it also poses a limitation in terms of the flexibility of timbre design.

We also think that the material of the pipe used should affect the timbre: future research will address this and try different materials (e.g., steel/aluminum tubes, wooden pipes, etc.).

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